

An Overview of Peri Implantitis

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Abstract:

Since 25 years, dental implants have evolved into an ascertainable technology for replacement of teeth. Since the dental implants have increased, incidences of peri-implant diseases are also growing. 2 forms related to peri-implant diseases; peri-implant mucositis and peri-implantitis. Several causative elements are accountable for the occurrence of peri-implantitis with bacterial biofilm performing the significant role. Proper assessment & proper treatment of peri-implant mucositis & peri-implantitis is important to avoid the implant loss. For the treatment of peri-implant diseases different conservative & surgical technique are accessible.

Introduction:

Since 25 years, dental implants have evolved into an ascertainable technology for the replacement of teeth. In spite of good results, almost all complication occurs at the starting of healing period and 1st year of loading these problems appears at alimентация and retaining period of implants.¹ The tissues around dental implants are vulnerable to infection that may cause implant loss.² Due to insufficiency of connective fiber to insert & dropped vascular force around implant, there is greater vulnerability to plaque induced inflammation.³ Biological difficulties affecting dental implants are mainly refer to inflammatory conditions associated with a bacterial challenge.⁴ 2 clinical forms may be distinguished: peri-implant mucositis and peri-implantitis. While the existence of an inflammatory lesion is a common feature of both conditions, while the second form has a feature of latter of bone loss.⁵ It's antedate that mucositis is followed by peri-implantitis.⁶

Peri-Implant Diseases

The tissue around an implant usually develops inflammatory lesions which are inclusively honored as peri-implant diseases.⁷ However the philanthropist can lose an implant, if these conditions are left undressed. Exploration indicates that 1 in 4 people who have dental implants are to be expected to have a peri-implant disease at certain point in their life (Wang et al., 2017).⁸

Peri-implant disease includes two forms:

- Peri-implant mucositis:** is a amendable inflammatory change of the peri-implant soft tissues with absence of bone loss.⁹
- Peri-implantitis:** is an inflammatory response associated with bone loss of supporting around an implant in function.⁹

Peri Implantitis

It is a contagious state of the tissues around implants with loss of bone and clinical feature of. It was first reported by Levignac in 1965.¹⁰ The word peri-implantitis was given by Mombelli in 1987.¹¹

The peri-mucosal seal which shapes all over the coronal area of an implant is around 3mm in corono-apical course & compresses of 2 ambit epithelium & connective tissue. Peri-implant mucosa varies from gingiva in its reduced vascularisation, reduced collagen quantity & absence of CT fibre inclusion; however the incendiary reaction to plaque is alike. The soft tissue seal that's analogous to the epithelial attachment of the tooth shield implant-bone interface by refraining from bacterial irritants, opposing mechanical pressure of restoration, mastication pressure & oral hygiene sustenance.¹²

Fig. 1: Schematic illustration of healthy periodontium and peri-implantitis lesion

Peri-implant mucosa	Physiological periodontium
Desmosomes and hemidesmosomes of epithelium and junctional epithelium (biological width) are linked with the contact surface	
Direct bone-to-implant contact	Anchoring system of root cementum, alveolar bone and desmodontic fibers
Subepithelially more collagen fibers and less fibroblasts/vessels	Subepithelially more fibroblasts and vessels
Parallel collagen fibers in relation to implant surface	Dentogingival, dentoperioatal, circular and transseptal fiber orientation

Table 1 Comparison between Peri implant mucosa and physiological periodontium¹³

FIGURE 1: Different mechanisms of the potential impact of peri-implantitis on systemic health.

Prevalence

According to some researches the occurrence of mucositis & peri-implantitis ranges from 5% - 63.4%. It is substantially grounded on varying study designs and population sizes.¹⁴

Zitzmann et al. concluded chances of occurrence of peri-implantitis is almost 6 times higher in people with a record of periodontitis as compared with patients with no record of periodontitis.¹⁵

After 10 years, 10% - 50% implants manifest the feature of peri-implantitis.¹⁶ According to Consensus Report of 6th European Workshop in Periodontology, Lindhe & Meyle showed that chances of mucositis is till 80% & of peri-implantitis amid 28%-56%.¹⁷

Mombelli et al., concluded that implanted patients had 20% chances of peri-implantitis & 10% in all inserted implants.¹⁸

Etiology

The leading cause of peri-implant diseases is microbial colonization. The plaque development pattern identified on oral implants is similar to those observed on teeth.¹⁹ The subgingival microflora associated with implant failures due to infection are the same as those associated with adult periodontitis. Subgingival staphylococci (*S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*) have been isolated from about 50% of gingivitis and periodontitis patients and from 55% of a small sample of ailing or failing implants.²⁰ A notable finding was that staphylococci were seen in 15% of cases with periimplantitis but only in 1.2% of periodontitis and 0.06% in gingivitis. As the difference was a statistically significant, the authors concluded that staphylococci play a role in some implant failures. Recently, microbiological DNA-probe scanning showed that people with peri-implantitis have high levels of periodontal microorganism like *Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Prevotella intermedia*, *Bacteroides forsythus* and *Treponema denticola*.²¹

Peri-Implantitis Risk Factors

1. Patient-Related Risk Factors

a) Periodontal Disease

Peri-implantitis is constantly presents with pronounced microbial variety and deeper peri-implant pockets exhibit notable microbial differences & advance situation of dysbiosis.²² Periodontal disease is linked with periimplantitis.²³ People having periodontitis have double threat of having peri-implantitis compared with healthy individualities.²⁴ Luckily, fruitful treatment of periodontal disease before the insertion of implant appears to have lesser chances of peri-implantitis²⁵ and is thus treated as important step in overall treatment plan.

b) Inadequate Maintenance Therapy

Supportive therapy significantly lower the risk of peri-implant biological complications, and a minimum recall interval of 5–6 months is recommended.²⁶ Factors used for risk assessment includes percentage of BOP, prevalence of active residual pockets, oral hygiene level, smoking habits and the presence of systemic or genetic conditions.²⁷ Individuals with high-risk profiles require 3 to 4 annual visits and their attendance is detrimental for prevention and early detection of peri-implantitis.²⁸

c) Cigarette & smokeless Tobacco

Smoking affects innate and adaptive immune reaction, decreases the host responses to microbial threat.²⁹ as well as affects wound healing.³⁰ Smoking also elevates the oxidative stress and inflammatory burden with pronounced changes in microbial flora. It mainly acts on affects implant's accumulation with periodontal pathogens like *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Fusobacterium nucleatum*.³¹ Apart from having harmful effect on smokers, bare exposure of environmental smoke to a person increases threat of periodontal disease by 28%.³² The association of water pipe smoking with periodontal disease have been proved by many studies.³³ Likewise water pipe smokers have higher chances of having periodontitis in comparison with cigarette smokers, but deterrmal effects are linked with the period and the amount of daily use.³⁴

d) Systemic Conditions

- **Diabetes mellitus** – Uncontrolled diabetes have a important role in the advancement of periodontitis.³⁵ This linkup is illustrated by vascular & cellular reactions, directing increased tissue loss & reduced healing reaction.³⁶ Alike responses is generated in periimplant tissues; developing increased chances of periimplantitis in people enduring from hyperglycaemia.³⁷ People with uncontrolled diabetes have around fortysix percent chances of having peri-implantitis, along with deeper periimplant pockets & excessive marginal bone loss, in contrast with people with having controlled diabetes.³⁸

- **Obesity**- an aberrant or inordinate body fat inflation with depleting effects on general health.³⁹ It's related with pronounced physiological shift, along with diabetes mellitus & coronary heart disease.⁴⁰ It is connected with distinct & sustained hyper-inflammatory state, leading to altered immune response & elevated level of proinflammatory cytokines, that negatively alter the periodontal tissues & alveolar bone levels.⁴¹ Researches have concluded that obesity leads to peri-implantitis. In comparsion with individualities having average body weight, obese people have increased index of BOP, deeper peri-implant probing depths & excessive marginal bone loss.⁴² The gravity of peri-implant inflammation is notably related with stage of obesity.⁴³

• Association between cardiovascular diseases and periimplantitis.

Patients suffering from heart disease have increased risk of having peri implant diseases and additional bone loss.⁴⁴

- Rheumatoid arthritis

Krennmair G et al concluded that with consequent connective tissue infection is linked with increased index of BOP and periimplant bone loss.⁴⁵ Korfage A et al showed that people with Sjögren's syndrome didn't had an increased risk of peri-implantitis still increased chances of mucositis in the case group may show increased vulnerability to peri-implantitis.⁴⁶

- Osteoporosis

A study concluded that there is an increased marginal bone loss & implant thread exposure with bisphosphonates absorption.⁴⁷ A current study concluded that a low-dose BP didn't exert influence on the bone around implant.⁴⁸

e) Genetic Factors

In spite of the common theory of some genetic predisposition to peri-implantitis, a clear linkup with some threat variable is yet to be resolved.⁴⁹ Interleukin-1 (IL-1) polymorphism is involved in the coding of 2 chief pro-inflammatory cytokines, IL-1 α & IL-1 β , along with anti-inflammatory IL-1 receptor antagonist. Growing quantity of both IL-1 α & IL-1 β is related with peri-implantitis, & there amount are associated with the gravity of the infection.⁵⁰

f) Occlusion

Excess load at, peri-implantitis concerned areas have excessive marginal bone loss in contrast with mucositis.⁵¹ The patterns of bone resorption diversified notably all over overloaded implants & with ligature caused peri-implantitis.⁵² The consequence of overburdening on periimplant bone levels is identified by sub-optimal implant positioning, defective prosthesis, insufficient bone level or its bad quality. Para-functional habits leads to increased non-axial occlusal forces which causes marginal bone loss.⁵³

Attrition & wear of natural dentition or prosthetic reconstructions probably acclimated for excessive occlusal load & parafunctional habits.⁵⁴

2. Implant Related Factors

a) Implant Surface

Implant's roughness & surface energy has an effect biofilm development, but everlasting-impact on the inflammatory response & bone stability still determinial.⁵⁵ some researchers showed that rough implants are vulnerable to peri-implantitis⁵⁶ while others didn't showed any notable variance between rough & moderately rough surfaces.⁵⁷

b) Ill fitted Prosthesis

The outline of prosthesis largely mainly adds to the implant's durability. Ill fitted prosthesis possibly hinders plaque control, which rises threat of progressing peri-implant infection.⁵⁸ An ill marginal fit have a deleterious effect which causes development of peri-implantitis.⁵⁹ the chances of having periimplantitis in cemented implant restoration is 3.6 times in contrast to screw retained.⁶⁰ It occurs because excess cement is left in the sub-mucosal region, mainly when resin luting agents is used.⁶¹ So, deep sub-mucosal margins must be evaded for proper transparency & way access for cement scrapping.⁶²

c) Peri-Implant Soft Tissue Conditions

The soft tissue situation over an implant may lead to peri-implant disease. People with thin periodontal phenotypes are susceptible to peri-implant mucosal recessions. The vulnerability of an implant's rough surface to the oral cavity impedes plaque control & increases bacterial adhesion, causing gain in the vulnerability to peri-implantitis.⁶³

d) Iatrogenic Factors

Implant malpositioning appears as an important peril for peri-implantitis. When an implant is positioned near about the natural teeth or to an another implant crestal bone resorption take place.⁶⁴

e) Inadequate Plaque Control

Patient taking steps to control the plaque impact implant's outcome. A high plaque score is companied with octuple rise in the vulnerability to peri-implantitis. The cumulation of dental plaque on implant & abutment surfaces causes peri-implant inflammation, called mucositis.⁶⁵

Etiopathogenesis of Peri-implantitis

The marginal inflammatory tissue response in implants is analogous to that seen in gingivitis and periodontitis of teeth. Once the plaque accumulation is started; neutrophils are signed to the periodontal pocket or the gingival crevice due to the chemotactic peptides, secreted by the bacteria. Likewise bacteria harm the epithelial cells, they beget epithelial cells to secrete cytokines that facilitate attraction of leukocytes mainly neutrophils to the crevice. The neutrophils inside the crevice phagocytose & digest bacteria and thus, take off the bacteria from the pocket. It degranulates if the neutrophil becomes overburden with bacteria. It results in tissue injury from toxic enzymes which are secreted from neutrophils. Finally, if there is an overburden of microbial plaque, the neutrophils and the barrier of epithelial cells won't be sufficient to control the infection. In such situation, the gingival tissue gets inflamed. However if inflammation increases from the marginal gingiva into the supporting periodontal tissues, it causes bone destruction & loss of attachment, which is known as periodontitis. Bacterial plaque products activate the differentiation of bone progenitor cells into osteoclasts & trigger gingival cells to secrete mediators that give same outcome. Certain host factors secreted by inflammatory cells are efficient in activating bone resorption in vitro & causes periodontal disease. It includes host produced prostaglandins & certain cytokines (IL-1, TNF- α etc).⁶⁶

Classification of Peri- Implantitis

The classification systems of peri-implantitis are:-

1. Classification based on distinct clinical stages⁶⁷

Early	Probing depth greater 4 mm (bleeding and/or suppuration on probing) bone loss less than 25 % of the implant length
Moderate	Probing depth greater or equal to 6 mm (bleeding and/or suppuration on probing) Bone loss 25% - 50% of the implant length
Advanced	Probing depth greater or equal to 8 mm (bleeding and/or suppuration on probing) Bone loss less than 50% of the implant length

2. Classification based on bone defects adjacent to dental implants highlighting the defect anatomy in the progression of the regenerative process⁶⁸

a. Closed defects	maintenance of intact surrounding bone walls
b. Open defects	Absence of 1 or more bone walls.

3. Classification based on the clinical status.⁶⁹

Staging	Definition
Stage I	Bleeding on probing & Suppuration & bone loss less than 3 mm beyond biological bone remodelling
Stage II	Bleeding on probing & Suppuration & bone loss less than 3 mm & greater than 5 mm beyond biological bone remodelling
Stage III	Bleeding on probing & Suppuration & bone loss greater than 5 mm beyond biological bone remodelling
Stage IV	Bleeding on probing & Suppuration & bone loss greater than or equal to 50% of the implant length beyond biological bone remodelling

4. Classification based on bleeding on probing, probing depth, percentage of bone loss and mobility⁷⁰

STAGE	Bleeding on Probing	Probing Depth	Bone loss (%) of implant length	Mobility	Proposed Treatment & Prognosis
STAGE 1	-	2-3 mm	10-25%	No mobility	No treatment
STAGE 2	+	4-6 mm	25-50% Vertical Horizontal combination	Grade 1	vertical defect <2-4 mm- GBR, osteoplasty Horizontal Defect < half of implant height - APF, GBR, osteoplasty Combination Defect: Bone augmentation and GBR. Prognosis is fair.
STAGE 3 Horizontal	+	6-8 mm	>50% Vertical Horizontal combination	Grade 2	vertical defect 2-4 mm-GBR, ABWG Defect > half of implant height - GBR and Augmentation. Combination Defect: Implant removal. Questionable Prognosis
STAGE 4	+	>8 mm	>50%	Grade 3	Implant removal Poor prognosis

APF- Apically positioned flap, GBR- Guided bone regeneration, ABWG- Autogenous bone wedge grafting.

5. Classification of retrograde peri-implantitis⁷¹

Class I (Mild)	Extends greater than 25% of the implant length from implant apex.
Class II (Moderate)	Extends 25 to 50% of the implant length from implant apex.
Class III (Advanced)	Less than 50% of the implant length from implant apex.

6. Classification based on defect morphology

a. Based on amount of bone loss with shaped of defect associated⁷²

- Class 1: Slight horizontal bone loss with minimal peri-implant defects
- Class 2: Moderate horizontal bone loss with isolated vertical defects
- Class 3: Moderate to advanced horizontal bone loss with broad, circular bony defects.
- Class 4: Advanced horizontal bone loss with broad, circumferential vertical defects, as well as loss of the oral and/or vestibular bony wall

b. Based on the configuration of the bony defect as⁷³

- Class I defect – Intraosseous
- Class II defect – Supra-alveolar in the crestal implant insertion area.

c. Based on type of bone resorption pattern.⁷⁴

- Class I – Horizontal
- Class II – Hey-shaped
- Class III a – Funnel shaped
- Class III b – Gap-like
- Class IV – Horizontal-circular form

Features of Peri-Implantitis

- Increased reddishness & swelling.
- Bleeding on probing
- Suppuration
- Peri-implant pocket (>4mm).
- Pain on mastication
- Supra occlusion at implant site
- Mobility – final grade of peri-implantitis (Mombelli & Lang, 1998)⁷⁵

Radiographic Characteristic:

Generally takes the form of saucer throughout the implant & is well defined (vertical bone destruction with periimplant pocket).⁷⁵

Diagnostic Parameters:

1. Radiographic Evaluation

The sustention of marginal bone height is believed pivotal for implant sustenance & frequently used as essential basis for implant's success. Vertical bone loss lowers than 0.2 mm yearly subsequently after the implant's 1st year of service is suggested as the significant basis for gain. For the precise evaluation of bone level alert rations, long-term sequence of standardized radiographs are needed. Suggested of radiograph 1 year after implant placement, but another radiograph is required to judge the range of marginal bone loss if clinical variable shows clinical feature of peri-implant disease.⁷⁵

2. Peri-implant probing

Stable fixed place is used on an implant abutment or prosthesis for a dependable dimension of attachment levels. Peri-implant probing must be averted in the first 3 months after abutment connection to evade the interference in healing & formation of soft tissue seal. The peri-implant probing attachment position matches nearly with radiographically assessable peri-implant bone level differences. Should be included in every maintenance recall session.⁷⁵

3. Bleeding on Probing

BOP shows inflammation of soft tissue either over natural teeth or implants. BOP is a bad determinant of advancement of periodontal disease though showing no existence at consecutive maintenance appointment perhaps is good negative seer of attachment loss. A favourable relation is assumed between BOP & histologic signs of inflammation at peri-implant place.⁷⁵

4. Suppuration

Large amount of leukocyte are present at implant site that which shows increasing gingival inflammation. Suppuration is closely linked to disease activity & indicates shows for the requirement of anti infective therapy.⁷⁵

5. Mobility

It is the sign of absence of osseointegration. Bone destruction can continue besides any notable signs of implant mobility till osseointegration is fully lost. Indeed if disease situation in the peri-implant tissues have grown implants can even show immobility because of enduring direct bone to implant contact. This variable helps to identify the last stage of osseointegration and may aid in choosing implant removal.⁷⁵

6. Implant Stability

Two non-invasive approaches developed are

a. Perio-Test

A non-invasive, electronic device which offers an assessment of the response of periodontium to determine the smack of load exerted on the tooth crown. A score more than 5 shows severe mobility & explanation (Mombelli & Lang, 1998).⁷⁵

b. Resonance Frequency Analysis (RFA)

It uses a sensor which is a fixed to the implant or abutment. The RFA value is a province of the firmness of implant in the adjacent tissues.⁷⁶

7. Plaque Assessment

Swelling & reddishness of marginal tissues is described from peri-implant infections. These peri-implant variables are grounded on periodontal indices like Sulcus Bleeding Index & Gingival bleeding Index. The bleeding propensity of the marginal peri-implant tissues may be evaluated by Modified Sulcus Bleeding Index. Quantity of plaque on implants could be evaluated by Modified plaque index.⁷⁵

8. Microbiology Test

Checking the subgingival microflora is suggested to decide the increased risk of periodontal disease or peri-implantitis. It is good to base systemic antimicrobial therapy grounded on microbiological data (Mombelli, 2002).⁷⁶

9. Peri-Implant Crevicular Fluid

MMP-7 & MMP-8 is considerably higher infected peri-implant sulcular fluid as collate with study individual. The amount of laminin-5 & Gelatinase B are increased at infected sites.⁷⁶

Management Modalities of Peri-Implantitis

The oral micro flora appears to be the describing element for the success or the failure of a dental implant. When implant surface is assailable to the oral cavity, get covers by a protein layer – the salivary pellicle – & are inhabited by oral microorganisms, forming a microbial biofilm. Surface debridement is essential for treating both periodontitis and peri-implantitis. Mechanical debridement of such surfaces has a less effect & clearly doesn't completely remove of all adhering microorganisms. Thus, additional peri-implant therapies, like antibiotics, antiseptics, & ultrasonic & laser treatments, are suggested to enhance the non-surgical treatment options of peri-implant mucositis & peri-implantitis. Regenerative procedures using a bone graft substitute in combination with a membrane is suggested in treating bone defects in advanced cases of peri-implantitis.

1. Local Debridement

The implant are suppose to be cleaned by instruments smoother compared to titanium, like polishing with a rubber cup & paste, floss, interdental brushes, or using plastic scaling instruments. These doesn't roughen the implant surface unlike metal & ultrasonic scalers.⁷⁷ Though implant surface damage can nearly be averted by using either ultrasonic scalers with a nonmetallic tip or resin/carbon fiber curettes, the presence of implant threads & or implant surface roughness may jeopardise the access for cleaning.⁷⁸

The research done by Karring et al. showed that sub-mucosal debridement alone, fulfilled by either an ultrasonic device or carbon fiber curettes, isn't sufficient for the disinfection of the surfaces of implants with peri-implant pockets greater than 5 mm & exposed implant threads.⁷⁹

1. Implant surface decontamination

Four implant surface decontamination ways were compared in a monkey model:

- (1) Air-powder abrasive technique followed by citric acid application
- (2) Air-powder abrasive technique
- (3) Gauze soaked in saline followed by citric acid application
- (4) Gauze soaked alternately in 0.1% chlorhexidine and saline.⁸⁰

Findings from an in vitro study associating photosensitization by toluidine blue solution and soft laser irradiation have pointed that elimination of bacteria from distinct titanium surfaces without modification of the implant surface was possible.⁸¹

Photodynamic therapy is a non-invasive approach that could be used to reduce microorganisms in peri-implantitis. Decontamination of affected implants with titanium plasma-sprayed or sandblasted/acid-etched surfaces may most fluently and effectively be achieved by applying gauze soaked alternatively in chlorhexidine and saline.⁸²

According to Schwarz et al., the Er:YAG laser and the combination of mechanical debridement/chlorhexidine are similarly efficacious at 6 months after therapy in significantly improving peri-implant probing pocket depth and clinical attachment level, but the use of the Er:YAG laser provides a significantly advance reduction of bleeding on probing compared with the adjunctive application of chlorhexidine.⁸³

2. Anti-infective therapy

Patients suffering from localized peri-implant problems in the absence of other infections may be campaigners for treatment by local drug-delivery devices. Local application of antibiotics by the insertion of tetracycline fibers for 10 days can give a sustained high dose of the antimicrobial agent precisely into the affected site for several days. The use of minocline microspheres as an adjunct to mechanical therapy is salutary in the treatment of peri-implant lesions, but the treatment may have to be repeated.⁸⁴ The study by Renvert et al. showed that the adjunctive benefits deduced from the addition of an antibiotic minocycline to mechanical debridement tend to be greater, although to a limited extent, than those attained by the combined use of an antiseptic (chlorhexidine) and mechanical debridement. The advancement in peri-implant probing depths attained by the adjunctive use of minocycline can be maintained during a short-term period of 12 months.⁸⁵

If the problem is generalized, specific microbiological information is collected and antibiotics are administered systemically. Lang et al. suggest the following antibiotic regimens: systemic ornidazole 500 mg bd for 10 days or metronidazole 250 mg td for 10 days or a once daily combination of metronidazole 500 mg and amoxicillin 375 mg for 10 days.⁸⁶

3. Surgical technique

Surgical resection is usually confined to implants placed in non-aesthetic sites. Surgical flap helps in complete debridement and decontamination of the affected implant. Surgical therapy was carried out, using:

- (1) Autogenous bone grafts covered by membranes,
- (2) Autogenous bone grafts alone
- (3) Membranes alone
- (4) A control access flap procedure showed that defects treated with membrane-covered autogenous bone showed significantly larger amounts of bone regeneration and reosseointegration than those treated with the other three procedures. However, membrane exposure is a frequent complication after such procedures. Exposure of porous e-PTFE membranes may result in bacterial penetration and lead to infection.⁸⁷

Conclusion

Use of dental implants for replacement of missing teeth has become the norm in oral rehabilitation in recent days. Though implants have shown effective and predictable results, increase in use of dental implants has also been associated with occurrence of implant failures of which the most common cause is peri-implantitis. Peri-implantitis is progressive destructive chronic diseases of bacterial or mechanical origin that affects hard and soft tissues surrounding the implant. The prevalence of peri-implantitis at implant level ranged between 6.5% -47% and prevalence at patient level ranged between 18.8% -47%.

Looking at etiology, dental plaque and associated micro-organisms has been universally identified as the primary etiologic agents. The second factor identified as etiology is the mechanical factors. Apart from these, a number of risk factors have been associated with peri-implant diseases like local factors (parafunctional habit, local anatomic factors, etc.), systemic factors (age, genetics, medical conditions, etc.), behavioral factors (oral hygiene maintenance, patient compliance). On analyzing the evidence for microbiologic profile of peri-implantitis, following micro-organisms were more prevalent *Porphyromonas gingivalis* (PG), *Prevotella intermedia*, *Treponema denticola* (TD), Looking into treatment of peri-implantitis both non-surgical and surgical interventions have been analyzed. Non-surgical therapy included alteration of implant surface, soft tissue debridement and adjunctive use of anti-microbial, lasers and host modulatory agents. Non-surgical therapy is effective only in eliminating the local etiologic factors and might not be effective in osseous defects. Surgical interventions include reflection of flap, debridement and use of various bone grafts material and membranes. With increase in awareness and demand for replacement of missing teeth with dental implants, peri-implant diseases are also increased.

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